

DEVELOPMENT OF MATMATICAL MODEL OF GAS FRACTION UNIT

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Abstract

Studies conducted in the oil refining industry have shown that a priori choice of a model from a particular class without identifying an object class to satisfy a given criterion when modeling technological processes and solving optimal control problems often leads to failures. Therefore, when creating an optimal control system for any technological process, first of all, it is necessary to determine the nature of changes in both external and internal material flows that characterize this process. As a result, a mathematical model of the object is built and the problem of its analysis is solved. The article is delivered the solution of the issue of building a mathematical model of a gas fractionation plant. The propane cylinder of a gas fractionation plant is taken as the object of research.

Keywords: mathematical model

Recently, as a result of the development of modern technology, the correct and more optimal control of complex systems has become possible. Optimal control of complex systems means obtaining products of high quality and quantity at low cost. For this, in addition to the technological devices to be used, it is necessary to build and apply the correct mathematical model of the system [1,2]

During the building of the mathematical model of the system, first of all it is necessary to study what parameters affect the product production. We should take the values of these parameters affecting the quality of the product as a limiting condition.

One of the main issues in the building of the model is the accurate measurement of the values of the parameters that affect the produced product. For this, measuring devices with high accuracy should be used [3,4].

Conditions of limitation:

$$\begin{aligned} 18.1 \leq x_1 \leq 20 \\ 56 \leq x_2 \leq 65 \\ 88 \leq x_3 \leq 119 \\ 58.1 \leq x_4 \leq 61.4 \\ 80.1 \leq y \leq 8.24 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where:

X_1 – Pressure ; kg/cm²

X_2 – Temperature at the top of the boiler ; °C

X_3 – temperature below the boiler ; °C

X_4 – Raw material consumption ; % mass

Y – Amount of PPF obtained ; % mass

We enter the initial statistical data (table 1) into the EXCEL program and indicate the area where the coefficients will be obtained. Then we select the statistics function from the functions section. Here we select the Line function. We enter the X and Y variables in the appropriate sections. We add 1 (TRUE) to the Const and Stats cells. And, finally, by pressing the Contr+Shift+Enter keys together, we obtain the coefficient of the model (Table 2).

The model is generally shown as follows:

$$Y = B_0 + B_1 X_1 + B_2 X_2 + B_3 X_3 + \dots + B_n X_n \quad (2)$$

Where:

$$B_0 = 10,31201$$

$$B_1 = 0,038733$$

$$B_2 = 0,01131$$

$$B_3 = 0,010447$$

$$B_4 = -0,07826$$

Since the mathematical model is as follows:

$$Y = 10,31201 + 0,038733X_1 + 0,01131X_2 + 0,010447X_3 - 0,07826X_4 \quad (3)$$

According to the results of the statistical analysis presented in Figure 1 the regression coefficient R is close to unity and the Fisher coefficient F exceeds the value of 4.8 our model is adequate.

$$R = 0.995472$$

$$F = 787.2442$$

Table 1

Initial statistics				
x1	x2	x3	x4	Y
18,1	56	88	58,1	8,01
18,2	56	89	58,2	8,02
18,2	56	89	58,3	8,02
18,3	57	90	58,4	8,03
18,3	57	91	58,5	8,04
18,4	57	92	58,6	8,05
18,4	58	93	58,7	8,05
18,5	58	94	58,8	8,07
18,6	59	95	58,9	8,08
18,7	59	96	59	8,09
18,8	59	97	59,1	8,1
18,8	60	98	59,2	8,11
18,9	60	99	59,2	8,12
19	60	100	59,3	8,13
19	60	101	59,4	8,13
19,1	61	102	59,5	8,15
19,1	61	103	59,6	8,15
19,12	61	104	59,7	8,16
19,2	61	105	59,8	8,17
19,23	62	106	59,9	8,18
19,3	62	106	60	8,18
19,3	62	107	60,1	8,19
19,4	63	108	60,2	8,19

Table 2

Obtaining coefficients in the Excel program				
x1	x2	x3	x4	Y
19	60	100	59,3	8,13
19	60	101	59,4	8,13
19,1	61	102	59,5	8,15
19,1	61	103	59,6	8,15
19,12	61	104	59,7	8,16
19,2	61	105	59,8	8,17
19,23	62	106	59,9	8,18
19,3	62	106	60	8,18
19,3	62	107	60,1	8,19
19,4	63	108	60,2	8,19
19,4	63	109	60,3	8,19
19,41	63	110	60,4	8,2
19,42	63	111	60,5	8,21
19,45	63	111	60,6	8,21
19,5	64	112	60,7	8,21
19,6	64	113	60,8	8,22
19,6	64	114	60,9	8,22
19,7	64	115	61	8,23
19,7	64	116	61,1	8,23
19,4	65	117	61,2	8,23
19,9	65	118	61,3	8,24
20	65	119	61,4	8,24
-0,07826	0,010447	0,01131	0,038733	10,31201
0,023052	0,003001	0,003394	0,015013	1,225969
0,99126	0,007342	#N/D	#N/D	#N/D
850,6641	30	#N/D	#N/D	#N/D
0,18344	0,001617	#N/D	#N/D	#N/D
#N/D	#N/D	#N/D	#N/D	#N/D

Regression statistics				
Multiple		0,995426892		
R – square		0,990874698		
Normalized R – squared		0,989616035		
Standard error		0,007238092		
Observations		34		

Analysis of variance				
df	SS	MS	F	F-operation
Regression	4	0,164974809	0,0412437	4,07562E – 29
Remainder	29	0,001519309	5,239E - 05	4,07562E - 29
The result	33	0,166494118		

Figure 1. Regression analysis

Since the mathematical model is as follows:

$$Y = 10,31201 + 0,038733X_1 + 0,01131X_2 + 0,010447X_3 - 0,07826X_4 \quad (3)$$

According to the results of the statistical analysis presented in Figure 1 the regression coefficient R is close to unity and the Fisher coefficient F exceeds the value of 4.8 our model is adequate.

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As a result, a propane cylinder is analyzed as a control object. Based on this analysis, the main mode parameters of the process are determined. A mathematical model is built using the correlation relation between the regime parameters and its adequacy is checked. [5-7]. Regression analysis has been confirmed the adequacy of the obtained model.

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